

METHODICAL PREPARATION OF STUDENTS FOR SPIRITUAL ACTIVITY USING THE RICH SCIENTIFIC HERITAGE OF OUR ANCESTORS

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Abstract: In the this article our ancestors left a rich scientific from the inheritance using students spiritual to the activity Methodical preparation with depends time demand issues discussion done.

Key words: Spirituality, education work, spiritual formation, our ancestors left a rich spiritual heritage.

INTRODUCTION:

Strengthening and developing the spiritual spirit of the people is the most important task of the state and society in Uzbekistan. Spirituality is instilled in a person with mother's milk, father's example, and ancestors' education. The great importance of mother tongue is that it binds people together as a symbol of spirituality. Proximity to nature, enjoying the beauty of the beloved country nourishes and strengthens spirituality. Spirituality becomes a powerful force only when it is based on a deep knowledge and understanding of the history, culture and tasks of its people. [5,18 b].

Education is of crucial importance in building a free civil, legal democratic society. Another important vital factor that directly affects the formation of spirituality is closely related to the education system . It is known that our forefathers considered knowledge, education and upbringing as priceless wealth as the most important condition and guarantee of human maturity and development of the nation. Of course, education is a product of consciousness, but at the same time it is the most important factor that determines the level of consciousness and its development, that is, it forms and enriches the spirituality of the people. We should not forget that the foundation of our future is created in the fields of knowledge, in other words, the future of our nation depends on the education and upbringing of our children today. For this, every parent, teacher, and coach needs to see a person first in the person of each child. Based on this simple requirement, we should accept that the main goal and task of the education field should be to raise our children to be perfect people who have the ability to think independently and broadly. This requires that education and training work be carried out harmoniously. Therefore, the destiny of a perfect person lies in the education of the young generation.

When we talk about the perfect generation of today, we can certainly say that the young people who are armed with new knowledge, have a rich spiritual world, recognize their identity, and respect our national values and traditions

are perfect individuals. It is not enough for students to be educated, they should also have humanity, patriotism, kindness, hard work, sincerity, nobility, and many other most beautiful human qualities. . If we look at our glorious history, we still need the rich spiritual and cultural heritage left by our ancestors. Without studying our past, we cannot understand who we are. Among our ancestors are Imam Al-Bukhari, Imam At-Tirmizi, Khwaja Bahavuddin Naqshband, Khwaja Ahmed Yassavi, Al-Farabi, Abu Raikhan Beruni, Ibn Sina, Al-Khorazimi, Mirza Ulugbek, Alisher Nawai, Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur and many of our scholars. We cannot promote the spiritual maturity of today's youth without introducing the rich heritage left by them. In this sense, it is permissible to quote the following words of our First President Islam Karimov: "The memory of history, the restoration of the objective and true history of the people, the beloved country, the territory of our country, the realization of national identity, so to speak, the restoration of national pride and occupies a very important place in the growing process [6, 2 b].

The concept of spirituality is very broad. Spirituality is not a material need for a person, nor is it a political necessity. Spirituality is a product of man before his essence. Here, First President IA Karimov explains the concept of spirituality as follows. "Spirituality is an incomparable force that calls a person to spiritual purification and spiritual growth, strengthens the inner world of a person, strengthens his will, completes his faith, awakens his conscience, is the criterion of all his views...", "The society we build It should guarantee the decent life and freedom of the people of Uzbekistan, restore our national values and culture, and ensure the spiritual and moral integrity of a person" [5,64 b].

In the system of higher education, the normative basis for systematizing the possibilities of educational materials for methodical preparation of students for spiritual activity in this field, improving the mechanisms of pedagogical development of their spiritual knowledge, skills and qualifications has been developed, and its material and technical base is expanding.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. In Mirziyoyev's decree "On the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" "On ensuring spiritual development and bringing the industry to a new stage, goal 71: Based on the principle of goodness and humanity - Actions to turn a healthy worldview and creativity into a national movement in the society by widely promoting the idea of "from strategy to development strategy". Development of scientifically based indicators for evaluation of spiritual education. About the use of interactive methods of education to turn schools into centers of true spirituality and enlightenment, culture" [1].

Today, as a result of the efforts of our President Sh. Miirziyoyev, great opportunities have been created to further improve the methodical preparation

of students for spiritual activities and prepare competitive personnel. In order to develop education, effective and high-quality pedagogical education technologies and tools are being developed and introduced. In the implementation of this mission of national importance, it is very important to reflect it in the "Pedagogy" programs provided for in the curriculum of higher education. Accordingly, by analyzing the curricula of the subjects of the pedagogical sciences included in the curriculum of the above-mentioned field of education, in the process of studying the majority of their departments, topics, questions, students will be taught to the younger generation. the possibilities of introducing ideas, trainings, and masterpieces of folk pedagogy related to ensuring spiritual and moral healthy growth, protecting the country, and the country were demonstrated. In particular, "Education and its types", "Ethical and mental education, formation and development of thinking", "Physical education", "Ecological, economic education", "Aesthetic education", "Ethical education in Eastern pedagogical education" of the "General pedagogy" in the course of studying topics such as "views", it was found that there are ample opportunities to introduce students to materials that encourage young people to strive for spirituality in all aspects of personal history [2].

In fact, in the process of studying the topic "Ethical views in Eastern pedagogical teaching", the analysis of the rich spirituality of our ancestors in the process of educating young people to be spiritually, morally and physically perfect is reflected in the masterpieces of folk art. they are sure that they have found it.

As mentioned above, spiritual education is one of the most important tasks for the society. As professors and teachers perform the main task of laying the foundations of education in the future, they should have deep knowledge and skills about our rich spiritual heritage. In educational sessions, students are taught to connect each lesson to the topic of the subject using the rich heritage left by our great-grandfathers, so that they deeply understand the incomparable contribution of our great-grandfathers in the development of today's sciences, and have a sense of pride in their hearts. they should create the ground for us to be excited. For this purpose, higher education institutions, in order for students to acquire spiritual knowledge in depth and thoroughly, based on the integration of science topics in educational subjects, in order to make the topic broader and more interesting, along with modern knowledge, our ancestors they should also deeply know our rich scientific heritage. It is then that students have greater opportunities to absorb spiritual knowledge.

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